

Microbiology In Schools

Curriculum

What Motivation?

Students

Interest ingrained in students

Future

Males / Females career paths.

Information insufficient to make career decision

A student pursues microbiology in spite of the school system, not because of it.

Guidelines

Teaching

Little time to teach microbiology

Students accept what's given to them

Examples

Pipettes in classroom

Dishwasher decontamination

Selected antibiotic cultures

Feeding students dangers

Exploration

Current System

No system is perfect.

Nexus Exploration

Provide opportunity to explore science

Overcome learning blocks

Maintaining standards

Success

Now I can satisfy my own curiosity for learning